

VISION OF BEGUM ROKEYA AND PRESENT EDUCATIONAL STATUS OF MUSLIM WOMEN IN WEST BENGAL : A TEXTUAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Begum Rokeya was Bengal's first Muslim feminist thinker, writer and educationist. She has a great contribution on women's independence and education. She confessed that the women specially the Muslim women are deprived and they don't have the minimum courageous attitude to face the challenges of daily life. For the lack of proper education, they have lost their self-confidence. She tried to educate the women so that they can use it as a weapon to rejuvenate themselves in the modern society. In Islam, women hold a prestigious place but in practice, it is not very common in the current world due to the discrimination and patriarchal attitude. She realized that women have been suffering a lot but no voices are arising against it. Rokeya tried to make people understand about the rights and freedom of women. Her one and only vision was to educate the women so that they would reach their fullest potentials as a human being and do the necessary things according to their own interest without depending on men. She mainly focused on expansion of female education in the Bengali Muslim society. She strongly believed that proper education would enlighten women and liberate their selves from the barriers of rigid patriarchal and sexist norms. She always raised her voice against discrimination and any type of torturing of women. Her main target was to emancipate the women of Bengal. She has a lot of activities for empowering women but the real fact is that she did not have any formal education or training. This paper seeks to analyze the vision of Begum Rokeya and educational status of Muslim women in West Bengal. The observer tries to explore it using various primary and secondary sources like documents analysis, research articles, books, newspapers etc.

Keywords: Feminist thinker, Freedom of women, Patriarchal attitude, Social discrimination, Rational beings.

INTRODUCTION

In the History of women education in undivided India, Begum Rokeya (1880-1932) was a great personality for guiding the Muslim women and showing the right way in which they can go ahead towards the modernity denying all the social and religious obstacles. Her tireless efforts and struggle opened the door of education among the Muslim women. So, she

is considered as the pioneer of women education in Muslim society of undivided Bengal. She was born in 1880 at Pairabondh village in the Rangpur district of undivided Bengal. She belongs to an Islamic religious family and lived behind the curtain from the age of five like all female members of her family. She was crazy for her study in the early days of her life. At that time, when women education was neglected and less important, Rokeya's brother helped him secretly to learn Bengali and English. In the year 1896, she got married by force when she was sixteen years old. She got married with a widower named Khan Bahadur Syed Sakhawat Hossain who was nearly forty years old. But, fortunately Sakhawat Hossain was a liberal and progressive minded man. He helped Rokeya every moment in studies and made all the arrangements for her studies. He also helped her to publish her writings in Indian periodicals at that time. After her husband's sudden death in 1909, she went into the great sea of misery. But she did not break down. She accepted the challenges with full of confidence and continued her further activities. She struggled hard and devoted her life for emancipation of Bengali Muslim women. She felt the need of women education and founded a girl's school for that purpose. She died of heart problem on 9th December 1932. She was really a pathfinder for the upliftment of women education in Bengal. She worked hard till the last day of her life. She wrote so many books, essays, novels, utopias, poems, humor and satirical articles on the rights of women and other social issues of that time in both the language Bengali and also English. Her husband was the main inspiration in this regard. She established a school for Muslim girls in Kolkata and tried to enshrine her ideologies among the students. She started her literary career with a story Pipasa (The Thirst) in 1902 and also wrote two famous essays named 'Motichur-I' and 'Motichur-II'. In 1924, she wrote a novel named 'Padmarag'. She had few works in English also. Sultan's Dream (1908) is one of them. Through all her activities, she tried to educate and liberate the Muslim women in Bengal.

BEGUM ROKEYA: PIONEER OF WOMEN EDUCATION AND LIBERATION

Rokeya was a modern, self-educated woman with progressive thoughts and ideas. She observed the miseries of women and how they were deprived of education. She realized that awakening of women was a must to set them free from their miseries. She used her pen as a weapon of women education and wrote against the inhuman position of women in the society. She tried to make women aware of themselves. The women were not given freedom in the conservative society at Rokeya's time. The women could not live freely in the society. They were not so aware about their education and rights. Sometimes women themselves did not want to educate themselves and they were against female education. So, their awakening was not possible without removing the religious orthodoxy and social obstacles. Rokeya strongly believed that through education, a woman can be self-reliant and confident. For the fulfilment of that goal, she established a school (Sakhawat Memorial Girls School) and organization for women (Anjuman-e-Khawatin-e-Islam). She wrote several books, essays, poems in both Bengali and English. Through different activities, she has depicted the wretched condition of women in the family and in the society as well.

STATUS OF MUSLIM WOMEN IN BENGAL

Total number of Muslim women in West Bengal is approximately 12.16 % of total population. It cannot be neglected as they are also the part of Bengal. But their educational and socio-economic status are below then the average. Comparatively lower percentages of Muslim women literacy in West Bengal before 2001 and a little progress of Muslim women literacy in West Bengal after 2001 had been noticed. The literacy rate of Muslim women in West Bengal is lowest among all other persons in India and West Bengal, for the period from 1965 to 2015. There are several causes for lagging behind the Muslim women in West Bengal such as educational, social, economic, institutional, religious, cultural, and awareness related causes.

PRESENT EDUCATIONAL STATUS OF THE MUSLIM WOMEN IN WEST BENGAL

After passing seventy-three years of independence, a large number of Muslim women belong to the educationally backward, economically weak and politically marginalized section of the society. The least literacy rate is a common nature of the Muslim women in Bengal. They are lagging behind and not competing with other communities because of their attitude towards education. Among the 3.3 crore male literates, 74.56% are Hindus and 23.07% are Muslims and among the 2.77 crore female literates 73.89% are Hindus and 23.85% are Muslims (Times of India Report 31.12.2015). Muslim women were not educationally strong since the independence of India. The government of India tried to find out the reasons of educational and economical backwardness of Muslim Community through various committee and commissions. The Gopal Singh Committee was formed by the Government of India in 1983 and the committee recommended that the Muslims are a backward community in India as well as West Bengal. Sachar Committee report (2006) announced that ‘Poverty is the main cause of poor education among the Muslim in India’. Ranganath Mishra Commission (2007) declared that “Muslims are socially, economically, educationally, politically and culturally underprivileged and are far behind the main stream of Indian society”. According to the Sachar Committee report, only 4% Muslim children are enrolled in recognized school and 9% of this total attends some short of school recognized or unrecognized and remaining 91% do not have any school to attend. Those enrolled hardly complete school education and 90% of the enrolled get dropped out. The literacy rate and the levels of education of Muslim in West Bengal are so far from the national average rate. According to the Census 2011, the literacy rate in West Bengal is 77.08% which is significantly higher than national average rate of 74%. But the Muslim literacy rate is only 57.18% which is so far from the national average rate. In Bengal, Muslim literacy (57.18) is lower than Schedule Tribe literacy 57.92% (Census, 2011). In West Bengal, Muslim literacy rate are less than other socially disadvantaged community. It is terrible event that Muslim women literacy (49.75%) is less than the Muslim literacy (57.18%) in west Bengal. Muslim male literacy rate is 64.61 % whereas

female literacy rate is 49.75% (Ghosh & Kar, 2017). The situation of rural Muslim women is very worse in relation to their literacy. Only 47.87% rural Muslim women are literate and literacy in urban area is 59.23%.

CAUSES OF LAGGING BEHIND OF MUSLIM WOMEN

According to the study of Rahaman and Bhuimali (2011), they mentioned that “among various reasons, the major reasons for educational backwardness among the Muslim community have poor economic condition. One of the important causes of lagging behind in education of Muslim women is socio-cultural perspective. Lack of true education and awareness among the parents of Muslim women is a big obstacle for having education among the Muslim women. According to the report of “National Education Survey”, Muslim women are seven times behind the Hindu women in high school education and they are nine times behind them in post high school. Most of the parents of Muslim girls believe that education of their girls is not so important due to wrong moral and cultural values. Primarily girls are enrolled in school education but before completion of a certain level, they are withdrawn and forced to get married at an early age. Some parents are not interested to send their girls to co-ed school because of parda system and some parents are interested to send their girls private Madrasha only for ritual education. They think that the purity of girls would have lost during the time of higher education or university education or travel aboard. This is why they did not support higher education for women.

CONTRIBUTION OF BEGUM ROKEYA FOR EDUCATING MUSLIM WOMEN IN BENGAL

Rokeya educated herself with her tireless self-effort and progressive ideas. She felt deeply the misery of Muslim women and their deprivation of education. She tried to make women feel that education is the only way for removing all the miseries of life. At a time, she was habituated with ‘Purdah’ system but always she was against conservative and Male dominated society. She said, “I worked and I wrote. I wrote about the evils of society. I wrote about the evils of Purdah, about the foolishness and cruelty of customs... I wrote about the laws that restrict women, and I wrote about the weakness of Bengalis. (Zaman 18-19)”. She wrote several books, short stories and articles like Sultan’s Dream (1908), Motichur- I (1904), Motichur-II (1922), Freedom Fables, Abarodh Basini (1931), Padmarag (novel-1924), God Gives Man Robs (essays-1927) etc. One of the great contributions of Begum Rokeya was “Sakhawat Memorial Girls School” in 1909. She tried to make a new era for the Muslim Community and worked as a real path finder through her various activities.

CONCLUSION

On basis of the above discussion, it can be concluded that Muslim women in West Bengal are lagging behind from the mainstream in various aspects of progress. There is no doubt that the education has the super power to build a progressive and liberal society. Though the Muslims are the part of the society, they should change their mind set and get involve in modern education system. Different researches show that Muslims specially the Muslim women of Bengal are in a backward position not only from educational status but also socio-economic situation, employment, health status, political awareness and political participation etc. Muslim women are very much deprived of the various opportunities due to cause of dominating power of male. It is a very common picture in the society that the education of Muslim women is very low, inadequate and negligible. The backwardness of any community in any part of the country is nothing but destroying of national resources and it is a big loss of a nation. To overcome all the problems of Muslim women, importance must be given to develop their self-awareness, self-reliance, self-corrections and self-realization. The over-all development of Muslim women is urgent need of the hour. For a holistic development and change of the Muslim society, they need to come out from their low level of aspiration, frustration, cultural retardation, societal depression. Begum Rokeya strongly realized the situation of Muslim women and tried to root out all the problems of them and shows a proper way of modern life.

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